

HOW INDIA'S PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS ARE TURNING GREEN: A COMPARATIVE REVIEW OF GREEN BANKING INITIATIVES IN PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS

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Abstract

Green Banking has been a ground breaking revolution, which is reshaping the public perceptions of banking, finance and sustainability. It also has emerged as a vital strategy to align financial systems with environmental sustainability. This study investigates green banking initiatives of the selected Indian public sector banks. Through a qualitative content analysis of secondary sources such as sustainability reports, annual reports and official disclosures, the study evaluates Green Banking Initiatives (GBI) using a predefined framework. The conceptual framework categorizes GBI into - green product development (GPD), Green internal operations (GIP), and Green corporate social responsibility activities (GCSR) of the selected banks. The study also analyzed the financial flow of these selected banks towards renewable and non-renewable projects. Findings of the study reveal that these banks are increasingly aligning their operations with environmental goals by financing renewable energy projects, digitizing banking services, and promoting eco-conscious lending practices. While continued growth in green investments offers hope, the easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal-projects underscores the potential risk. The banks encounter several challenges including limited customer awareness, regulatory gaps, and concerns over greenwashing. The study provides strategic recommendations for regulatory reforms, capacity building, and innovation in green financial instruments. The insights contribute to the growing body of literature on sustainable banking and provide a roadmap for enhancing environmental performance in India's banking sector.

Keywords: Green Banking, Sustainable Banking, Green Banking Initiatives, Public Sector Banks, Environmental Finance, Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation due to unchecked industrialization, urbanization, and population growth has triggered global concern over sustainability (Rehman et al., 2021). In this context, the financial sector—particularly banks—plays a crucial intermediary role by allocating capital and influencing investment decisions that directly impact the environment (Ikram & Akhtar, 2021). As major financiers of commercial projects, banks contribute significantly to ecological footprints, both through direct resource consumption (e.g., paper, electricity) and indirectly by funding carbon-intensive industries (Nizam et al., 2019). According to the Report of Rainforest Action Network 2016-21 “some of the major international banks have contributed more than \$10 trillion to Coal financing”.

Currently India is the third largest emitter of carbon dioxide, placing a significant responsibility on the country to reduce the carbon emission. India has been also witnessing numerous environmental issues due to the rapidly increasing population, unplanned use of efficient technologies, and poorly managed waste management system (Rahman et al., 2023). India has huge infrastructure needs and power demand and its expected soar high in the coming years (Renewable energy vs Coal Report, 2024). Therefore, India is at a critical juncture. The country should decide whether it will build its future on highly polluting power plants such as coal or thermal or invest in renewable sources such as – Solar and Wind. Which are among the most affordable and cost-effective means of generating power in the country. India's future trajectory will depend upon its regulatory and political will and its ability to access sustainable finance pools. This is why monitoring green banking initiatives of banks is important. While continued year on year growth in renewable & sustainability investments offers hope, the easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal projects underscores the significant potential risks (Renewable energy vs Coal Report, 2024).

The concept of green banking has emerged in response to growing environmental and social challenges. Green banking refers to the adoption of environmentally sustainable practices by banks in their operations, product offerings, and financing decisions. United Nation Environmental Program (UNEP) 2014 defined, "green banking as any financial activity that result in efficient use of resources, reduce environmental risks, and socially inclusive". The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) introduced guidelines in 2007 to integrate sustainability into banking operations, encouraging Indian banks to adopt green policies and support projects aligned with environmental objectives (Trehan, 2015). Despite this, the adoption of green banking in India remains uneven and often superficial (Rakshitha & Chaya, 2023).

This study is significant for understanding green banking Initiatives in Public sector banks for several key reasons. First the banking sector must support the sustainable projects in order to lessen their carbon footprint. Despite India being the seventh most vulnerable country with respect to climate extreme (Eckstein et al., 2019) as well as the third largest emitter of greenhouse gases at present (Gupta et. al., 2022) there is limited research on how its bank can contribute to sustainable growth. This study contributes the role of public sector banks in response to climate change and environmental degradation. Second, since GBI is still in its infancy in India, with limited adoption by banking sector (Sharma & Choubey, 2022). This study offers significant insights to practitioners and policy makers aiming to formulate sustainable policies. Third from the research insights the banks can gain competitive edge by promoting green banking programs over conventional banking, through which banks can enhance customer satisfaction as well as long term corporate benefits.

Finally, this study drawing the GB framework from Sharma & Choubey (2022) proposes a unique research framework, which would be interesting to examine in new context in India for the first time.

The focus of this study is evaluating the green banking practices of five leading Indian public sector banks - State bank of India, Bank of Baroda, Punjab national bank, Canara bank and Union bank of through the lens of green product development (GPD), green internal processes (GIP), and green corporate social responsibility (GCSR). The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** What are the green banking initiatives implemented by the selected public sector banks in India?
- **RQ2:** Which commercial banks are actively involved in financing Renewable and Non-renewable projects?
- **RQ3:** What are the major challenges these banks face while implementing green banking programs?

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Global Perspective on Green Banking

Initially the Green banking was introduced in the year 2009 in state of Florida (Sharma & Choubey, 2022). Over a period of time several banks throughout the globe have adopted ecofriendly green banking programs for financing as well as green transformation of internal operation (Mir & Bhatt,2022). For example, countries like Bangladesh, Brazil, Colombia, and Indonesia have begun implementing green banking practices in line with their respective policy frameworks (Rahman & Akhtar, 2016). The Bangladesh banks for instance implemented several green banking policies such as paperless banking, green financing, solar roof and green mortgage. These programs not only able to increase funding for environment friendly projects but also discourages initiatives that may harm the environment (Hasanur *et. Al.*, 2023). In Japan GX (Japan Climate Transition Bonds) plan focuses on green finance, investment in renewables, energy efficiency and circular economy (Rehman *et al.*, 2021). GX bond aims to decarbonise sectors like iron and steel, chemical, power, gas, oil, pulp and paper, cement etc. (Nomura, 2023). China has made a significant progress in green banking initiatives, especially in green bonds and green financing. They have excelled in green credit, with banks supporting firms with robust green strategies, (Chen & Zhao, 2021). Fintech supports green finance by improving credit access, bridging information gaps, and building trust, especially in farming communities (Rahman *et al.*, 2023). Green bonds are key to funding a wide range of environmental projects beyond just renewables and green buildings (Rahman *et al.*, 2023). China holds over 20% of the global green market, second only to the USA (Chen & Zhao, 2021).

2.2 Green Banking in the Indian Context

To meet international standards, the RBI has introduced several guidelines aimed at promoting green banking. Key objectives include developing green banking policies, financing environmentally friendly industries, integrating green practices into internal controls, and setting exposure limits for industries with harmful environmental impacts

(Trehan, 2015). Swasthika A. (2023) Studied various green banking initiatives of commercial banks in Karnataka (A southern state in India). SBI has implemented a number of initiatives in this area, including the Green Channel Counter, increased commitment to reaching carbon neutrality, online money transfer, wind farms, and so on, (SBI Sustainability Report, 2024) ICICI (Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India) Bank's green strategy includes digital banking services like internet banking, auto, and home finance to reduce environmental impact. The bank also promotes energy conservation through measures like double-sided printing, recycling, and using CFL lighting (Kumar & Akula, 2023).

Green banking strategies such as using environment friendly products, adopting sustainable internal processes, and improving CSR initiatives to make green finance more effective for the environment and economy (Sharma & Choubey, 2022). A conceptual model was proposed in the past research to examine the impact of green banking initiatives—such as green product development, green CSR, and green internal processes—on outcomes like green brand image and green trust (Sharma & Choubey, 2022). The study also reveals valid information regarding why Indian banks are not able to meet the international standard as most of the Indian banks face major challenges. However, green banking initiatives have created positive word of mouth, which helped in creation of green image amongst the customers, that helped in achieving customer loyalty and banks profitability (Sharma & Choubey, 2022).

The banking sector is increasingly adopting innovative green products such as online and mobile banking, digital bill payments, green mortgages, eco-friendly credit cards, green certificates of deposit, and partnerships with local institutions that support environmental initiatives—reflecting the growing momentum of green banking in India. (Gupta, 2015). Bihari and Pandey (2015) examined efforts by public and private sector banks in India to adopt sustainable banking practices. Their research looked at the use of paperless banking by these institutions and found that banks are implementing diverse strategies to enhance their image in line with green banking principles.

The benefits of green banking are indeed immense. Green investments actually outperform traditional portfolios in the long run and it provides better return to the investors (Sharma & Choubey, 2021). Green banking commences proactive actions to address environmental issues while advancing along with efficient use of natural, human, renewable, and non-renewable resources (Mir & Bhat, 2022).

Despite having a lot of benefits of Green Banking, the adoption of green banking still is in very novel and infancy stage in developing economies like India (Rehman *et al.*, 2021). Several factors contribute to this low level of adoption such as lack of updated knowledge, scarcity of global measurement tools, low level of technology adoption (Rehman. *et.*, *al.* 2021). The other major challenges are lack of awareness regarding green banking initiatives, lack of education and presence of green washing (Meenakshi & Akanksha, 2021). State owned commercial banks or public sector banks (PSBs) displayed less inclination towards adoption of green banking practices compared to private sector banks (Khatun *et.*, *al.* 2021).

The existing literature has explored the green banking initiatives across various developing countries, such as Sri Lanka (Shaumya & Arulrajah, 2016), Bangladesh (Siddik *et al.*, 2022), Pakistan (Bukhari *et al.*, 2020), Nepal (Mishra & Aithal, 2023), China (Weber *et al.*, 2023), and India (Meenakshi & Akansha 2022). However, there is a dearth of research on adoption of green banking in India. This limited research resulted in lack of understanding among policy makers and in industry encouraging low carbon emission economy. Therefore, the adoption of green banking initiatives in India warrants deeper investigation. This study aims to explore green banking practices adopted in selected public sector banks to address the existing empirical gap in the literature

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In the context of sustainable finance, green banking encompasses a broad spectrum of initiatives, from eco-friendly internal operations to the financing of environmental projects. Sharma and Choubey (2022) identified green product development (GPD), green internal process (GIP), and green corporate social responsibility (GCSR) as the three core components of GBI. Drawing from Sharma and Choubey (2022) this study adopts a three-dimensional conceptual model to examine green banking initiatives in Indian public sector banks:

3.1 Green Product Development (GPD)

This dimension refers to the introduction of financial products that directly support environmentally responsible behavior.

These include green loans, renewable energy financing, green mortgages, electric vehicle loans, and eco-friendly investment instruments such as green bonds and mutual funds (Gupta *et al.*, 2025).

3.2 Green Internal Processes (GIP)

This aspect involves internal reforms to minimize the environmental impact of banking operations. Key initiatives include digitization of services, energy-efficient branch infrastructure, installation of solar-powered ATMs, e-statements, and document management systems to reduce paper use (Mir & Bhat, 2022).

3.3 Green Corporate Social Responsibility (GCSR)

GCSR covers activities outside the direct profit motive, aimed at promoting environmental sustainability and financial inclusion.

Examples include tree plantation drives, bio-toilet construction, digital literacy initiatives, and preferential lending to green startups or rural self-employment programs (Nizam *et al.*, 2019).

By evaluating these three dimensions this study offers a structured analysis of green banking adoption and its systemic integration.

Table 1: Framework for Green banking Initiatives

Source: Sharma and Choubey (2022) and Sindhu (2015)

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research Design

The study employs a **qualitative, exploratory research design** grounded in secondary data analysis. This approach is appropriate for assessing policy-driven practices such as green banking, where rich textual data from institutional reports provide critical insights (Sharma & Choubey, 2022). The research was conducted in two phases: first, a detailed literature review on green and sustainable banking; second, the collection of data on Indian banks from various secondary sources.

4.2 Data Sources

Data were collected from publicly available sources, including:

- **Annual Reports** (2022–2024)
- **Sustainability and CSR Reports** of the selected banks
- **Official websites** and investor presentations
- **Reputable financial media** (e.g., Business Today, Moneycontrol)
- **Academic literature** from Scopus-indexed journals

These documents were examined for disclosures related to green initiatives, financing mechanisms, infrastructure investment, employee training, and CSR activities.

4.3 Sampling

The sample includes the **top five Indian public sector banks** by market capitalization as of 2025. These banks were selected due to their size, regulatory importance, and extensive disclosure practices.

Table 2: Top five Indian public sector banks

Public Sector Banks	
Banks	Market Capitalisation
State Bank of India	INR 5.4 trillion
Bank of Baroda	INR 760 billion
Punjab National Bank	INR 730 billion
Canara bank	INR 660 billion
Union Bank of India	INR 580 billion

(Source: Moneycontrol, 2025)

4.4 Data Analysis

A thematic content analysis was conducted using the predefined framework of GPD, GIP, and GCSR. The data were organized into themes and subthemes, enabling cross-case comparison of initiatives and their impact. The study also triangulates findings with existing literature to ensure contextual validity.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The green banking initiatives of – State bank of India, Bank of Baroda, Punjab national bank, Canara bank and Union bank of India were evaluated across the three conceptual dimensions: Green Product Development (GPD), Green Internal Processes (GIP), and Green Corporate Social Responsibility (GCSR).

5.1 Green Product Development (GPD)

State Bank of India Being India’s largest public sector bank, SBI recognizes its role in driving India’s progress towards sustainable development and it has become the role model for the Indian Banking Industry (SBI, 2024).

According to **sustainable report of SBI**, (2023, 2024) SBI has introduced several green banking initiatives to promote sustainable finance.

- The **SBI Green Rupee Term Deposit** aligns with RBI guidelines, utilizing proceeds to support eligible green activities (SBI Annual Report, 2023).
- **Surya Shakti** for businesses provides financing for solar rooftop and ground-mounted grid-connected systems (SBI Sustainability report, 2024).
- **The PM Surya Ghar Initiative** offers simplified, affordable loans for households to install solar panels (Annual reports SBI, 2024).
- **Biofuel projects** under the National Policy on Biofuels 2018, supporting biomass suppliers, aggregators, and biofuel extraction plants (SBI Sustainability report, 2024).

- **Windmills Installations** - as part of its direct sustainability efforts, SBI has installed 10 windmills with a total capacity of 15 MW across Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, and Gujarat (Neeraja & Joseph, 2021)

Bank of Baroda (BoB)

- **Bob Earth Green Term Deposits Scheme:** It enables the flow of credit towards Green Activities. This scheme offers depositors dual benefits of stable & secure financial returns and the opportunity to contribute to a greener planet (BoB, annual report, 2024).
- **Solar Housing Loan:** Through these initiatives the bank offer loan in rural/semi urban areas for solar rooftop (BoB Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC):** The Bank has introduced the Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) the rupees digital variant to facilitate customer digital payments (BoB, annual report, 2024).

Punjab National Bank (PNB)

- **PNB Green Car Loan:** The purpose of the product is to purchase of new electronic car for the use of personal and commercial (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Solar Housing Loan:** The purpose of the loan is the installation of rooftop solar system at residential house to the customer (PNB, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **PNB Green Ride:** The purpose of the loan is to provide loan for green transport operators of rickshaws (new entrants) and also to create employment opportunities for the micro borrowers (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).

Canara bank (CB): Canara Bank is one of the largest public sector banks, established in 1906 and the bank was nationalized in 1969.

The sustainability report of Canara Bank, 2023 & 2024 mentions several Green Initiatives such as

- **Canara Green Wheels** program which offers loans for electric vehicles (EVs), encouraging sustainable transportation and reducing air pollution (CB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Solar rooftop installations** and the installation of stand-alone solar agricultural pumps under the PM-KUSUM Scheme (CB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Green Deposit Policy and Lending Framework,** Canara Bank mobilizes funds for projects focusing on renewable energy, energy efficiency, clean transportation, green buildings, and other environmentally friendly initiatives (CB Annual report, 2024).
- **MSME Vahan Financing** for the purchase and installation of solar off-grid systems, solar lighting, and solar water heating systems (CB, Sustainability report, 2024).

Union Bank of India with more than 153 million customers. Demonstrating its commitment to the environment, Union Bank of India became a founding member of the Indian Green Building Council (IGBC), a leading green rating body established by the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), (Union Bank, 2024).

- **Green Finance** Union Bank of India was the largest lender in 2023-24 for renewable projects such as solar and wind energy, providing more than INR 4500 crore in Loans. (Coal vs Renewable Energy report 2024)
- The **Union Solar** program supports the installation of solar power plants for captive use, offering collateral waivers and concessional interest rates. In FY2023, the Bank sanctioned around \$10.5 million under this program, contributing to carbon emission reduction and the promotion of renewable energy (Union bank Sustainability report, 2024).

5.2 Green Internal Processes (GIP)

The internal greening of operations includes digitization, energy-efficient branches, and renewable energy usage:

State Bank of India (SBI) established a **Social and Governance (ESG) and Climate Finance Unit**, a dedicated business unit guiding the bank's climate finance efforts toward a net-zero target by 2055. Installation of solar panels on its buildings and ATMs to improve energy efficiency.

- **Insta Plus Savings Account**, which uses video-based customer identification to minimize paper usage and promotes digitalisation (SBI Sustainability report, 2024).
- The **YONO 2.0** platform functions as a digital bank, offering a wide range of banking services while supporting the bank's sustainability goals (SBI Annual report, 2024).
- **SBI e-Mudra** provides digital green loans to microentrepreneurs, fostering employment growth and financial inclusion. (SBI Sustainability report, 2024).

Bank Of Baroda

- **Digital Repository:** Paperless banking is a major green initiative involving creation of digital repository of all critical documents and approval process in a digital format (BoB, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Solar Energy rooftop:** 177 Branches in rural/semi urban areas are being run on Solar Energy reducing approx. 3500 Tons of Carbon Dioxide Emission (BoB, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Bio-gas Plant:** This Bio-gas plant reduces the need for LPG and practices a Waste to Energy recycling model (BoB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Paperless Account Opening:** During FY'24, the Bank opened 91.85 Lakhs new CASA accounts with digital document (BoB, Sustainability report, 2023).

Punjab National Bank

- **Rooftop solar energy plants** at various Bank's buildings (PNB, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Electric Vehicle Charging stations** at all the office buildings (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Rain Water Harvesting systems & Sewerage Treatment Plants** have been installed in the majority of our owned buildings to conserve rain water for future usage (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).

Canara bank

- **Canara ai1 mobile app & Digital Banking Units (DBUs)** promote paperless transactions, along with e-lounges and e-governance platforms, contributing to environmental sustainability in banking (CB Annual report, 2024).
- **Electric vehicle charging infrastructure** at its head offices, supporting sustainable transportation (Sustainability report, 2024).
- **Document Management System (DMS)** facilitates paperless workflows, reducing paper usage and enhancing both staff productivity and customer experience (CB Sustainability report, 2024).

Union Bank of India

- **Digital loan approval**, the Bank offers advanced digital solutions such as instant loan approvals and digital payments to enterprise customers (UB Annual report, 2024).
- **Video KYC**, thousands of accounts have been opened through a dedicated Video KYC Cell. **WhatsApp Messenger** services like account balance inquiries and cheque status checks, with over one million users and 4.5l million enquiries (Sustainability report, 2024).
- **green vehicles** usage among staff members such as electric, hybrid, or CNG vehicles (Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Indian Banks Blockchain Infrastructure Company (IBBIC)** to implement blockchain technology, aiming to digitize services and reduce loan approval times (UB, Annual report, 2023)

5.3 Green Corporate Social Responsibility

State Bank of India: According to CSR Network, (2024) SBI's green corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives focus on financial inclusion, sustainability, and environmental conservation

- **Stand-Up India Scheme** Through this scheme SBI provides loans to SC/ST and women entrepreneurs for their first greenfield ventures, fostering inclusive economic growth (SBI, CSR report, 2024).

- **Self-Help Group (SHG) Financing** - funding women-led SHGs to promote sustainable livelihoods and gender equality (SBI, CSR report, 2024).
- **Tree Plantation Drive**, aiming to plant 5 million trees (SBI, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Construction of 4,000 Bio-Toilets** (SBI, Sustainability report, 2023).

Bank Of Baroda

- **Business Correspondent (BC) model:** In order to provide universal banking services especially to rural, semi urban and urban poor at an affordable cost (BoB, Sustainability report, 2023).
- **Community development and social welfare:** supporting education, healthcare, environmental sustainability, women empowerment, and rural development in backward regions in India (BoB, Sustainability report, 2024).

Punjab National Bank

- **PNB PALAASH:** Planting of approximately 1.10 lakh plants in the ongoing tree plantation drive through PNB PALAASH (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **PNB VIKAS:** Village Adoption Scheme, socio-economic empowerment through setting up 76 RSETIs (Rural Self Employment Training Institute) & 12 Farmers' Training Centres. During the FY 2023-24, a total of 60,721 persons were trained in RSETI centres out of which 47,911 belong to BPL Families and 47,899 were women (PNB, Sustainability report, 2023, 2024).
- **Rural Self Employment Training Institutes (RSETIs):** There are 76 RSETIs (under the aegis of MoRD) and 2 Rural Development Centres (PNB initiatives) operating in India that are engaged in providing training to rural population and their families for skill upgradation to undertake self-employment ventures (PNB, Sustainability report, 2024).

Canara Bank

- **plantation drive** planted millions of saplings across India (CB, Sustainability report, 2024).
- **cleanliness drive** in public spaces, schools, colleges, and Anganwadi centres in cities like Prayagraj and Bangalore (CB, Sustainability report, 2023, 2024).
- **Awareness program** consists of seminars, workshops, and training on cybersecurity and digital banking to more than 1,000 teachers and students (CB, Sustainability report, 2023).

Union Bank of India

- **Union Bank Social Foundation (UBSFT)** focuses on rural development, inclusive growth, and supporting governmental efforts to enhance access to healthcare, education, and livelihood prospects for underprivileged populations (UBI, Sustainability report, 2024).

- **The Rural Self-Employment Training Institutes (RSETIs)** promote skill-building in rural areas, empowering individuals with certifications and employment opportunities, ultimately contributing to the economic advancement of rural communities (Union Bank Sustainability Report, 2024).

Most Dominant Green Banking Initiatives Amongst Selected PSBs

Table 3: Summary of Most dominant Green Banking Initiatives amongst selected PSBs

Green Banking Initiatives	Most dominant Green Banking Initiatives amongst selected PSBs
Green Product Development	a) Financing Renewable Energy Projects b) Financing Green Vehicles c) Subsidized loan for green transition d) Accepting Green Deposit e) Rewards for green purchase f) Offering sustainable investment portfolios
Green Internal Process	a) Paperless transition b) Internet/Mobile banking c) Digital Repository and Reporting d) Green ATMs e) Solar Rooftop f) EV and supporting infrastructure g) Green Data center h) Blockchain and AI technology to digitize services
Green CSR	a) Tree plantation drive b) Financing the disadvantage section of the society c) Rural skill training center d) Financial inclusion e) Creating green awareness programs

Source: Authors work

The above table summarises the most prevalent Green Banking Initiatives across selected banks in terms of green product development, Green Internal process and Green CSR. After analysis the above mentioned GBI have emerged as most prevalent among the selected PSBs.

As revealed in the table in GPD the most prevalent green banking programs are – Green lending which was directed to finance sustainable projects, financing EVs, low rate of interest for green transioning and offering green portfolios for investments.

In GIP the most dominant Green Banking programs are paperless banking which is due to adoption of mobile banking, digital repository, Green ATMs, solar rooftop of the branches of the banks, green data centers and integration of Blockchain and AI technologies to digitise services.

The most prevailing green initiatives through GCSR are Plantation drive which is incorporated by all the banks, financing SHG led by Women, Rural skills training centres, financial inclusion and creating green awareness programs

Figure 1: Green Banking Initiatives of PSB

Source: Author's calculation

The above graph highlights that of the total green initiatives activities 47% consist of green product development, 40% consist of Green internal process and 13% consist through Green CSR. Therefore, majority of the green activities are happening through green financing.

We have seen that most of the green financing was directed to financing renewable energy projects, financing electric vehicles Loans, green mortgages for energy-efficient houses, subsidized loans for green transition-related investments and projects, and facilitating and supporting carbon credit trading transactions, among others.

Green internal process was identified as second most green banking activities, this is due to the major shift to paperless transactions among banking institutions, with the high adoption of digital and mobile banking enhancing both customer satisfaction and banking efficiency.

Sustainable Development Finance (SDF) of the Selected PSBs

This following table represents total lending of banks towards sectors such as renewable energy, green buildings, agriculture, MSMEs, and social infrastructure.

Table 4: Trend of SDF from 2020 to 2024

Year	SBI (₹ Cr)	BoB (₹ Cr)	PNB (₹ Cr)	CB (₹ Cr)	UBI (₹ Cr)
FY20	190576	60257	75808	58956	61841
FY21	206582	61527	84578	62487	67837
FY22	224366	73515	91331	72669	78587
FY23	258719	98896	107053	90258	97558
FY24	313683	123035	132982	119108	122428

Figure 2

Source: Authors Calculation

Over the past few fiscal years, the selected banks have demonstrated robust growth in financing sustainable initiatives. SBI (State Bank of India) has shown a consistent upward trend, significantly increasing its value from ₹190,576 Cr in FY20 to ₹313,683 Cr in FY24, while PNB (Punjab National Bank) has similarly registered strong growth by rising from ₹75,808 Cr in FY20 to ₹132,982 Cr in FY24. BoB (Bank of Baroda) and Union Bank have also experienced substantial growth, particularly during FY23 and FY24, which indicates a recovery or expansion phase. Meanwhile, Canara Bank has improved its performance, albeit at a slightly less aggressive pace compared to the leaps observed in SBI and PNB.

Financial Flow of Banks Towards Renewable and Non-Renewable Projects

India is currently the world's third largest emitter of carbon dioxide, placing a significant responsibility on the country to reduce the carbon emission. India being a developing country and with its highest population of 148 crore, has a huge infrastructure needs and power demand and it's expected to soar higher in the coming years (Renewable energy report, India, 2024). Therefore, India is at a critical juncture. The country should decide whether it will build its future on highly polluting power plants such as coal or thermal or invest in renewable sources such as – Solar and Wind. Which are among the most affordable and cost-effective means of generating power in the country (Coal vs. Renewable energy report, 2024).

India's future trajectory will depend upon its regulatory and political will and its ability to access sustainable finance pools. This is why monitoring green banking initiatives of banks is important. While continued year on year growth in renewable & sustainability investments offers hope, the easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal projects underscores the significant potential risks (Coal vs. Renewable energy report, 2024).

Currently India’s total installed non-fossil fuel energy capacity has reached at 188 GW. This includes solar, wind, hydro and nuclear. This means it will be difficult for India to reach its goal of 500 GW of cumulative installed capacity from non-fossil fuel (Renewable energy report, India, 2024).

Financing for Renewable Energy and Sustainable Projects

Total funding for renewable energy projects has been growing and it has increased by 51% in 2023-24 compared to 2021-22, reaching a total of INR 30,255 crore (USD 3663 million).

The commercial banks of India supplied INR 20,625 crore (USD 2497 million) to renewable energy projects, representing the majority of such loans (68%).

Amongst this the Union bank of India is the largest lender for renewable energy projects providing INR 4500 crore (USD 545 million) in loans.

Table 5: Green Financing in 2023-24

Green Financing in 2023-24		
	Loan Size (INR Crore)	Loan Size (USD million)
Solar	14,814	1793
Hybrid	13,773	1667
Wind	1,668	202
Total	30,255	3,663

Source: Bloomberg data base

Solar energy sector received the highest fund with INR 14,814 crore. The value of solar lending doubled compared to 2022-23 level, which was INR 7,361 crore.

This solar lending accounts 49% of renewable funding. NTPC green energy ssecured funding for the largest loan. The lenders were union bank of India and Axis bank.

Table 6: Green Project Finance by Banks

Green Project Finance (2023-24)	
Lender	Loan Size in INR Crore
Union Bank of India	4500
Cooperative Rabo bank (Mumbai)	3175
Axis Bank	3063
World bank	1239

Source: Bloomberg data base

In 2023-24, the commercial banks in India provided a total of INR 30,255 crore (USD 3663 million) for the renewable energy financing. The total capacity of all these projects amounted close to 8.84 GW.

The share of funding provided by PSB was 27% Union Bank of India was the largest lender for renewable projects, providing more than INR 4500 crore in Loans.

Financing for non-renewable energy (Coal-Linked) in 2023-24

Table 7: Financial supports of commercial banks for Coal lined projects

Banks	Loans & Underwriting (INR Crore)
Jefferies Financial Group	16,784
State bank of India	1,991
Kotak mahindra Bank	1,495
Punjab national bank	418
Bank of Baroda	24.6

Source: Bloomberg Database

In 2023-24, INR 25,945 crore (USD 3141 million) was provided in loans and underwriting for 10 Indian coal-linked companies. Underwriting plays a crucial role in facilitating the flow of capital to coal companies. By underwriting bonds or shares financial institutions help coal companies secure necessary funds. This indirect funding can be substantial support for funding coal related activities. Banks headquartered in US provided the majority of corporate finance (65%) to coal linked companies in India in 2023-24. Notably Jefferies Financial groups provided nearly 65% of total corporate finance to coal-linked companies like Adani and JSW energy. The State Bank of India was the largest corporate lender in India for allocating INR 917 crore loan and INR 1074 in Underwriting services. Followed by Kotak Mahindra bank providing around INR 1495 crore and Punjab National Bank with INR 418 crore. US ranked second globally in coal financing after China.

Figure 3: Share of Total Financing: Renewable vs. Non-Renewable projects

Source: Author's calculation

In the above pie chart, we can see that total funding for renewable energy projects represents 54% i.e. INR 30,255 crore (USD 3663 million). INR 25,945 crore (USD 3141 million) i.e 46% of total finance was provided for non-renewable (coal based) companies

in the year 2023-24. SBI stands the largest corporate lender for coal expansion plan. While continued year on year growth in sustainable energy offers hope, the easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal underscores the significant potential risk. Therefore, the government of India and RBI should implement coal exclusion policy which is currently not yet implemented by private and public financial institutions. According to a report of IEEFA, 2024 Indian banks are far behind in terms of formulating coal divestment policy. Only two commercial banks have formulated a coal exclusion policy – The Federal bank in 2021 and Suryoday Small Finance.

6. CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING GREEN BANKING INITIATIVES

There are a lot of challenges while implementing green banking initiatives in the Indian Banking Industry:

1. **Lack of Awareness:** The concept of 'Green Banking' suffers from low awareness levels among both bank staff and their clientele, according to The Boston Consulting Group's 2017 findings. Specifically, a study revealed that 66% of bank customers either do not know what Green Banking is, or confuse it with digital banking services (Rahman *et al.*, 2023)
2. **Green Washing:** Happens when the banks try to take advantage of the new trend of 'Going Green', without actually making any real changes. It's all about appearing to be Green. These have led to consumers doubt towards environmental advertising and has led to increase in negative influence on green banking (Sharma & Choubey, 2021).
3. **Lack of Transparency:** Many of the Indian banks do not clearly outline their investment policies and don't disclose their carbon footprint. There is no regulatory authority, who do sustainability claim verification (Kumar & Akula, 2023).
4. **Affordability Barrier:** Smaller banks find it difficult to offer competitive rates and services and meet sustainability goals. Therefore, policies which will make green banking more accessible is must (Swasthika A. 2023).
5. **Short run & high cost of funding:** Many banks in India have short term & high cost of funding which prevent them from providing more affordable financing to their borrowers for sustainable projects (Pak & Kim, 2021). Therefore, making it commercially not viable. Green bank's foremost goal is to promote sustainable projects that may not necessarily generate high profit. Therefore, compensating financial stability in the long run (Pak & Kim, 2021).
6. **Low expected earning:** Many MSME enterprises exhibit reluctance to adopt green banking practices as implementing these Green Banking as implementing these Green Banking programs involve high initial cost. Apart from this the realisation of expected earnings from these projects from these projects are very uncertain, (Giridhar & Sudhakar, 2017).

7. SUGGESTIONS

To advance environmental sustainability and foster a low-carbon economy, it is imperative to strengthen green banking initiatives in India. Based on the analysis, the following recommendations are proposed for the effective implementation of green banking practices:

- 1. Regulatory Framework Development:** Establish comprehensive, clear, and enforceable regulations that discourage environmentally harmful practices while incentivizing green banking initiatives. Policy measures such as tax benefits and subsidies should be designed to encourage banks to finance eco-friendly projects and investments.
- 2. Green Banking Guidelines:** Develop and maintain robust guidelines for green banking that provide explicit directives for integrating sustainable practices into the daily operations of financial institutions. These guidelines should outline best practices and standards for ecological responsibility.
- 3. Capacity Building:** Invest in education and training programs to enhance the expertise of banking professionals in green finance, environmental risk assessment, and sustainable banking methodologies. Capacity-building efforts will equip employees to effectively support the transition to environmentally responsible banking.
- 4. Green Financial Products and Services:** Expand the portfolio of green financial products, including green credit cards, loans, and mortgages, tailored to the needs of businesses and industries engaged in sustainable and environmentally friendly practices.
- 5. Digitization and Paperless Operations:** Promote the adoption of digital banking solutions to reduce paper usage in customer interactions and internal operations. This transition aligns with sustainable practices and enhances operational efficiency.
- 6. Public Awareness Initiatives:** Conduct extensive public awareness campaigns to highlight the significance of green banking and its societal and environmental benefits. Utilize various platforms, such as bank websites, targeted promotional campaigns, and attractive offers, including reduced interest rates, to engage stakeholders.
- 7. Dedicated Green Banking Units:** Establish specialized green banking departments within financial institutions to ensure the systematic and effective implementation of environmentally friendly initiatives.
- 8. Increased Funding for Green Projects:** Enhance funding allocations for environmentally beneficial projects and actively participate in corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives that align with sustainability goals.
- 9. Monitoring and Evaluation Systems:** Develop robust mechanisms for the continuous monitoring and evaluation of green banking initiatives. Conduct periodic

audits and reviews to ensure adherence to established green banking policies and identify areas for improvement.

- 10. Sustainable Banking Index:** Create a Sustainable Banking Index to assess and rank banks based on their performance in green banking activities. Such an index could act as a motivator for financial institutions to improve their sustainability performance and contribute to environmental goals.

These recommendations aim to create a conducive environment for the growth and integration of green banking practices, fostering a sustainable financial ecosystem in India that aligns with global environmental objectives.

8. CONCLUSION

India is currently the world's third largest carbon dioxide emitter and it has the highest population in the world. Being a developing country, India has a huge infrastructure and power demand and it's expected to soar higher in the coming years. Therefore, at this critical juncture, India should decide whether it will build its future on unsustainable way or invest in green infrastructure and renewable energy. Green banking acts as a critical pathway for India to align India's needs with sustainable development. Therefore, this study aimed at investigating the green banking initiatives of Indian public sector banks. We have examined the green banking Initiatives of State Bank of Indi, Bank of Baroda, Punjab National Bank, Canara Bank, and Union Bank of India. These are top five public sector banks with highest market capitalisation. A thematic content analysis was conducted using predefined framework of Green Product Development, Green Internal Process and Green CSR. The data were organised into theme, subthemes and enabling cross case comparison of initiatives and the impact. Based on the analysis the major finding can be concluded as follows.

First, the most prevalent Green Banking Initiatives through Green Product Development are green lending for sustainable projects, financing EVs, incentivising green transition and offering green portfolios for investment. In Green Internal Process – banks are enabling sustainable green programs such as – eliminating paper work, mobile and internet banking, digital repository, Green ATM, solar rooftop of bank branches and integrating Blockchain an AI technology to digitise services. Through Green CSR, banks are participating in Planation drive, Financing SHG of women, rural skill centre and creating green awareness programs.

Second, the study identifies the financial flow of the commercial banks towards the renewable and non-renewable projects. Findings reveal that the renewable energy projects have attracted a total of INR 30,255 crore i.e. 54% of total energy projects financing. Union Bank of India is the largest lender for renewable energy projects providing INR 5400 crore in 2023-24. However, the major challenge is continuous expansion of funding of dirty industries such as Coal projects companies. Banks headquartered in US provided the majority of corporate finance (65%) to coal linked companies in India in 2023-24. In India SBI was the largest corporate lender allocating

INR 1991 crore through loans and underwriting services. Therefore, easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal underscores the significant potential risks. The Reserve Bank of India should implement the coal exclusion policy, which is not yet implemented by private and public financial institutions.

Third, several challenges persist, including limited customer awareness, regulatory gaps, and concerns over greenwashing. The study provides strategic recommendations for regulatory reforms, capacity building, and innovation in green financial instruments. The insights contribute to the growing body of literature on sustainable banking and provide a roadmap for enhancing environmental performance in India's banking sector.

9. IMPLICATIONS

This study provides valuable information on how the Indian PSBs responding to the climate change challenge. The following specific implication can be made from the study. First green lending and digital banking are the most dominant activities across all the selected banks, the nature of the implementation is largely influenced by regulatory contexts. Second, while continued year on year growth in sustainable energy offers hope, the easy availability of funds for expanding dirty projects such as coal underscores the significant potential risk.

10. LIMITATION AND DIRECTION FOR FUTURE STUDIES

This research work was carried out to investigate the green banking initiatives of the selected public sector banks in India and to identify some of the major challenges while implementing them. There were certain constraints under which the research was completed. The research was purely based on secondary data from various Annual Reports, Sustainability Reports, ESG Reports and different bank's websites. Therefore, we used only the published data & information from the selected banks. Future research may on primary data & empirical investigation of the green banking initiatives of Public and Private banks in India.

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